

STUDIES IN CHALKONES: CHALKONES DERIVED FROM
HYDROXYACETYL BENZOIC ACIDS

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2-Hydroxy- and 4-hydroxy-5-acetylbenzoic acids have been condensed with various aldehydes in presence of alkali and the corresponding chalkones containing carboxyl group have been prepared for the first time.

The easy accessibility of 2-hydroxy- as well as 4-hydroxy-5-acetylbenzoic acids on account of the systematic investigation of the Fries migration of 2-acetoxy- and 4-acetoxy-benzoic acids (Shah and Shah, this *Journal*, 1949, 28, 237) opens the way through suitable reactions to the synthetic preparations of various heterocyclic compounds containing carboxyl group. As a part of the comprehensive scheme for synthesising such compounds, the present investigation was undertaken.

A considerable amount of work has been done on the chalkones containing different groups. Chalkones containing hydroxy and methoxy groups (Geissmann and Clinton, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1946, 68, 697; Wheeler and co-workers, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1937, 866; 1938, 1320; Venkataraman and co-workers, *ibid.*, 1935, 866; 1936, 569; Lal, this *Journal*, 1939, 16, 296; Shah, *J. Univ. Bom.*, 1942, 109), nitro and amino groups (Egler and Dorant, *Ber.*, 1895, 28, 2497; 1902, 35, 1065; Baeyer and co-workers, *Ber.*, 1882, 15, 2856; 1886, 16, 1963; Hansrupe *et al.*, *Brit. Abs.*, 1897, i, 371; *Ber.*, 1901, 34, 3527; *Brit. Abs.*, 1906, i, 754; Tanasescu, *ibid.*, 1936, 1110; *Chem. Abst.*, 1946, 42, 2622) and halogens in the molecule (Kostanecki *et al.*, *Ber.*, 1898, 31, 710; 1896, 29, 244; Kunckell, *Ber.*, 1911, 44, 3654; Barnes and Payton, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1936, 58, 1300) have been studied by several workers. But the chalkones containing carboxyl group have practically remained uninvestigated. The work described here is concerned with the preparation of such chalkones.

2-Hydroxy- and 4-hydroxy-5-acetylbenzoic acids were condensed with various aldehydes in presence of alkali (caustic potash solution). The reaction was found to take place smoothly, the corresponding chalkones being obtained in good yield.

Thus it is clear that the presence of carboxyl group does not diminish the reactivity in the above chalkone formation. However, on account of the reversible nature of the reaction (Shriner and Kurosawa, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 52, 2538) the concentration of alkali greatly affected the yield of the chalkones. Thus for example, in the condensation of 2-hydroxy-5-acetylbenzoic acid with benzaldehyde, the use of different concentrations of alkali showed that higher concentrations of alkali reduced the yield; while in the case of anisaldehyde, salicylaldehyde and *m*-hydroxybenzaldehyde, the reverse was found to be the case. To get the maximum yield of the chalkones, the condensations were carried out under various conditions and by suitable adjustment of the conditions like concentration of alkali, temperature and period of reaction, good yield of the chalkone could be obtained.

The notable properties of these chalkones are that they are bright yellow or red compounds with high melting points. They all dissolve in concentrated sulphuric acid with red coloration and give yellow or orange solutions in alkali. They also dissolve slowly in sodium bicarbonate solution. With alcoholic ferric chloride the chalkones derived from 2-hydroxy-5-acetylbenzoic acid give characteristic reddish violet coloration and those derived from the 4-hydroxy isomer give reddish brown coloration. Generally, they are moderately soluble in alcohol and acetic acid, while sparingly soluble in non-aqueous solvents.

EXPERIMENTAL

Chalkones derived from 2-Hydroxy-5-acetylbenzoic Acid

4-Hydroxy-5-carboxyphenylstyryl Ketone.—Potassium hydroxide solution (15 c.c., 40%) was gradually added to a mixture of the keto-acid (5 g.), benzaldehyde (4.5 g.) in alcohol (30 c.c.) with shaking and cooling. The reaction mixture was then kept overnight at room temperature. The resulting orange solution was diluted with water (300 c.c.) and acidified with cold dilute hydrochloric acid (1 : 1). The solid was collected and crystallised from alcohol as yellow needles, m.p. 238°, yield 4.5 g. (Found: C, 71.4; H, 4.4. $C_{16}H_{12}O_4$ requires C, 71.6; H, 4.5 per cent).

The condensation was repeated using higher concentrations of alkali (60%, 80%) but the yield of the chalkone was much reduced.

4-Hydroxy-5-carboxyphenyl-4'-methoxystyryl Ketone.—The acid (5 g.) was similarly condensed with anisaldehyde (5 g.) in presence of alkali (30 c.c., 80%). The solid obtained as before was crystallised from alcohol as yellow lustrous needles, m. p. 189°, yield 5.0 g. (Found: C, 68.1; H, 4.6. $C_{17}H_{14}O_5$ requires C, 68.4; H, 4.7 per cent).

The above condensation was tried with lower concentrations of alkali but the yields were not satisfactory.

4-Hydroxy-5-carboxyphenyl-2'-hydroxystyryl Ketone.—The acid (3 g.) was condensed with salicylaldehyde (3 g.) in presence of alkali (20 c.c., 80%) as in the previous case and the chalkone obtained as before was crystallised from dilute alcohol in red prisms, m. p. 190°, yield 2.0 g. (Found*: C, 63.7; H, 4.4. $C_{16}H_{12}O_5$, H_2O requires C, 63.6; H, 4.6 per cent).

As before, in this condensation lower concentrations of alkali led to the diminution of yield of the chalkone.

4-Hydroxy-5-carboxyphenyl-2'-methoxystyryl Ketone.—This chalkone was obtained by condensation of the acid (1 g.) with *o*-methoxybenzaldehyde (1 g.) in alcohol (15 c.c.) using potassium hydroxide (25 c.c., 40%); the mixture was heated on a water-bath at 90° for half an hour and left overnight. The bright yellow solid isolated as before was crystallised from acetic acid as bright yellow fibrous needles, m. p. 243° (decomp.), yield 0.8 g. (Found: C, 68.2; H, 4.5. $C_{17}H_{14}O_5$ requires C, 68.4; H, 4.7 per cent).

4-Hydroxy-5-carboxyphenyl-3'-hydroxystyryl Ketone.—The keto-acid (1.5 g.) was condensed with *m*-hydroxybenzaldehyde (1.2 g.) in presence of alcohol (15 c.c.) and potassium hydroxide (10 c.c., 80%) as above.

The chalkone crystallised from nitrobenzene as pale yellow leafy crystals, m. p. 207°, yield 0.6 g. (Found: C, 67.5; H, 4.3. $C_{16}H_{12}O_5$ requires C, 67.6; H, 4.2 per cent).

This condensation was also investigated under various conditions and heating on a water-bath was found necessary.

4-Hydroxy-5-carboxyphenyl-4'-hydroxystyryl Ketone.—The keto-acid (2 g.) was condensed with *p*-hydroxybenzaldehyde (1.5 g.) in presence of alcohol (15 c.c.) and potassium hydroxide (10 c.c., 65%), the reaction mixture being heated on a water-bath at 75° for 1½ hours. The substance obtained as before was boiled with hot water and the residual chalkone crystallised from dilute alcohol as yellow clusters of needles, m.p. 252°, yield 1.3 g. (Found: C, 63.3; H, 4.1. $C_{16}H_{12}O_5$ requires C, 67.6; H, 4.2 per cent).

Chalkones derived from 4-Hydroxy-5-acetylbenzoic Acid

2-Hydroxy-5-carboxyphenylstyryl Ketone.—To a suspension of 4-hydroxy-5 acetylbenzoic acid (2 g.) in alcohol (50 c.c.) and benzaldehyde (2.0 g.) caustic potash solution (25 c.c., 40%) was gradually added with shaking and cooling. The reacting mixture was left overnight at room temperature. It was then diluted with water and acidified with cold dilute hydrochloric acid. The solid crystallised from acetic acid as yellow rectangular plates, m.p. 224°, yield 2.5 g. (Found*: C, 71.2; H, 4.4. $C_{16}H_{12}O_4$ requires C, 71.6; H, 4.5 per cent).

2-Hydroxy-5-carboxyphenyl-4'-methoxystyryl Ketone.—This chalkone was prepared by the above method from the keto-acid (2 g.), anisaldehyde (2.5 g.) in alcohol (50 c.c.) using potassium hydroxide solution (30 c.c., 60%). The reaction mixture was heated on a water-bath for 5 minutes and left overnight at room temperature. The flocculent solid obtained as before was crystallised from acetic acid as yellow shining needles, m.p. 235°, yield 2.3 g. (Found: C, 68.0; H, 4.5. $C_{17}H_{14}O_5$ requires C, 68.4; H, 4.7 per cent).

2-Hydroxy-5-carboxyphenyl-2'-methoxystyryl Ketone.—The keto-acid (2 g.), *o*-methoxybenzaldehyde (2.0 g.) and alcohol (40 c.c.) were mixed with caustic potash solution (15 c.c., 60%). The chalkone obtained as before was crystallised from acetic

acid as yellow leaflets, m.p. 246° , yield 1.3 g. (Found: C, 68.2; H, 4.3. $C_{17}H_{14}O_3$ requires C, 68.4; H, 4.7 per cent).

2-Hydroxy-5-carboxyphenyl-3'-hydroxystyryl Ketone.—The keto-acid (1 g.) was dissolved in potassium hydroxide solution (25 c.c., 40%) and the solution of *m*-hydroxybenzaldehyde (1 g.) in alcohol (30 c. c.) added to it. The reaction mixture was heated on a water-bath for 30 minutes and left overnight at room temperature. It was acidified and the solid obtained was crystallised from acetic acid as deep yellow tiny needles, m.p. 230° (decomp.), yield 0.85 g. (Found: C, 67.4; H, 4.3. $C_{18}H_{12}O_5$ requires C, 67.6; H, 4.2 per cent).

2-Hydroxy-5-carboxyphenyl 4'-hydroxystyryl Ketone.—This chalcone was obtained from *p*-hydroxybenzaldehyde exactly in the same manner as in the case of *m*-hydroxybenzaldehyde described above, as yellow leaflets, m.p. 220° , yield 0.4 g. (Found: C, 67.2; H, 4.0. $C_{18}H_{12}O_5$ requires C, 67.6; H, 4.2 per cent).

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